

ANCIENT DOCTORS WHO TREATED DISEASES

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Abstract: *This article analyzes the most important stages of the history of ancient medicine, the scientific heritage of famous doctors who lived in ancient times, as well as their influence on modern medicine. In particular, the formation process of medical terminology and phraseology is deeply studied based on the medical knowledge created within the medical schools of ancient Egypt, India, China, Greece, Rome and Central Asia. The article provides information about the treatment methods, diagnostic methods, drug preparation techniques and hygienic views developed by ancient doctors, and their contribution to the modern medical education, practice and health care system is revealed.*

Key words: *ancient medicine, heritage of doctors, heritage of Hippocrates and Galen, Sushruta Ayurveda, Chinese medicine, evolution of medical terms, phraseological units.*

Аннотация: *в данной статье анализируются важнейшие этапы истории древней медицины, научное наследие знаменитых врачей, живших в древности, а также их влияние на современную медицину. В частности, на основе медицинских знаний, созданных в медицинских школах Древнего Египта, Индии, Китая, Греции, Рима и Средней Азии, глубоко изучается процесс формирования медицинской терминологии и фразеологии. В статье представлены сведения о методах лечения, методах диагностики, способах приготовления лекарств и гигиенических воззрениях, разработанных древними врачами, а также раскрыт их вклад в современное медицинское образование, практику и систему здравоохранения.*

Ключевые слова: *древняя медицина, наследие врачей, наследие Гиппократов и Галена, Сушрута Аюрвады, китайская медицина, эволюция медицинских терминов, фразеологизмы.*

The history of medicine includes the rich heritage of human experience and knowledge in the field of health care. Medicine is one of the sciences that plays an important role in human life and development.

Since ancient times, mankind has been looking for ways to cure various diseases. Therefore, the medical profession is considered one of the oldest and most sacred professions. Experiences and scientific views of ancient doctors played an important role in the formation of modern medicine.

Two people are famous from the history of Egypt - Erazistratus and Herophilus. Erazistratus examined the human brain and determined that it has hard and soft membranes, the surface of the brain is not flat, there are fluid storage cavities in the brain mass, and there are moving and sensing nerve vessels in the brain. Herophilus also began his career by studying anatomy. He carefully examined the brain, liver and heart. He examined the heart and observed that there are three periods in its movement - systole, pause and diastole. Egyptian healers prepared tinctures from herbs for drinking, rubbing with oils, compresses applied externally, massaging, prescribed baths, used bloodletting.

Ancient China developed unique methods for treating patients such as moxa, massage and acupuncture. Based on the moxa method, the skin of the diseased member is heated by burning various dried plants. In the massage method, the body is massaged with fragrant, oily substances.

This method has been used in various joint diseases and to increase the strength of the body. According to ancient Chinese healers, there are 360 points in the human body. When needles are inserted into these points, the patient does not feel pain and recovers from the disease. Acupuncture is also based on the principle of receptor action.

In addition to the generally known medicines in nature, they discovered new and very effective medicines from plants and animals. For example, the famous ginseng plant is one of the greatest discoveries of Chinese nature. Among the medicinal substances obtained from animals, panthocrine (pantocrine) substance obtained from the horn of a deer can be shown in the first place.

Three Ayurvedas are known in ancient Indian history. These are Atreya Ayur Veda, Charaki Ayur Veda and Sushruta Ayur Veda. Among these, Sushruta Ayur Veda is particularly noteworthy. The book describes the structure of the human body, its nature, issues of health care, identification of diseases and determining the causes of their origin. In Sushruta Ayur Veda, symptoms of more than 1500 diseases are described, methods of their detection are indicated. Sushruta was the first in the history of medicine to fully describe the symptoms of the inflammatory process. These include swelling, redness, increased temperature, pain, and decreased function of the inflamed organ. In ancient Indian medicine, the surgical method was very developed. Especially Sushruta was a very skilled surgeon. Surgeons carried out methods of removing a stone that appeared in the bladder, operating on a hernia, amputating an arm or leg that was severely injured and became unfit for work, and operating on cataracts.

The greatest achievement is plastic surgery. Such operation methods were used only in Indian medicine at that time. Sushruta himself was especially famous in the field of plastic surgery. Sushruta very cleverly implemented the method of plastic reconstruction of organs such as nose, ears, and lips. In ancient Greek medicine, the

(3rd international scientific and practical conference)

famous Hippocrates divided people into species. According to Hippocrates, people with different temperaments are susceptible to different diseases. For example, phlegmatic people feel better on dry and hot days and worse on rainy days. Since the climate of choleric is dry, they feel better when the air is humid. They cannot tolerate dry and hot temperatures. Melancholy suffer from diseases more often. Sanguines are the most resilient people. Hippocrates was the first in the world to introduce a medical history sheet for every patient. He introduced the doctors' oath. Also, the greatest work on medicine is the "Hippocratic Collection" and it was the main guide for every doctor.

The history of medicine reflects the long and complex development process of mankind in the way of health care and treatment of diseases. Shamans, healers, and early medical practices were formed in ancient times, and systematic medicine, which has a scientific basis, appeared later. The scientific legacy of great scientists such as Hippocrates, Ibn Sina, and Galen served as the cornerstone of the development of medicine. Today, medicine is becoming more perfect with the help of genetic engineering, artificial intelligence and high-tech equipment. At the same time, the study of the history of medicine is of great importance for doctors of the present and future generations. Knowing the process of formation of medical knowledge, understanding their historical roots increases the professional skills of medical specialists and creates a basis for scientific research.

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